

Chelation and fungitoxicity

Lallan Mishra

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005, India

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This review emphasizes the importance of chelation of heterocycles (benzimidazoles, 1,3,4-oxadiazoles, 1,3,4-thiadiazoles, 1,2,4-triazoles and uracils) with transition metal ions. The multifunctional heterocycles have a better chance to act as fungicides after chelation with metal ions or by pairing with nucleoside bases through weak bonding in the similar way as recently reported development of drug design using metal complexes as a ligand. The work done in author's laboratory in addition to brief support taken from the literature is discussed.

The interaction of metal ions with biomolecules and the function of metal ions in physiological systems is very complex and the precise mechanism of these interactions is almost unknown. On the synthetic systems, the review by Hancock and Martell¹ though describes an account of ligand design based on selective complexation with metal ions yet it is limited to ideas such as size-match selectivity in macrocycles, drop in stability due to increased size of chelate and steric strain etc. However, it is reported that the activity is a combination of steric, electronic and pharmacokinetic factors and it could be understood in the light of chelation theory². In this context, various heterocycles especially azoles (triazoles, thiazoles, imidazoles, pyrazoles etc.) occupy an important place owing to their versatile bioactivities due to the presence of multifunctional groups.

Development of new generation fungicides through chelation

In spite of all, the traditional approaches made in the development of fungicides evolving a large-scale screenings have now become obsolete. Thus, the development of a new generation of effective and environmentally safe fungicides is a complex problem to be solved only by the combined effort of basic researches in chemistry, biochemistry, biophysics and physiology of plants, animals and microorganisms.

The current approaches based on quantitative and qualitative relationships have however failed to produce novel generation of early and effective preparations. The main reason is believed to be the lack of comprehensive understanding of the molecular-interaction mechanisms between fungicides and living objects. In this context, it is of worth to mention that considerable progress made in the development of antitumor preparation is very much due to the studies on their molecular mechanism of action³. Comparison of such preparation with fungicide^{4,5}, readily showed that

the former is based on the principle of chemical action, while the latter involves only general biochemical manifestations of fungicidal activity. There can be common mechanism of germination-inhibition or fungal-inhibition rather than general law controlling the effects produced by a certain group of compounds on the active centre of particular enzymatic systems. It has also been mentioned that pesticidal activity is very much related to the occurrence of heterofunctional groups (including chelating agents) in the structure of pesticides that are responsible for the interaction with the vitally important metal ions. Such compounds have been given the conventional name heterofunctional pesticides (HFP)⁶ and they account for about 70–80% of the fungicides currently used in the laboratory and in the field. Some of the electron donor group present in heterofunctional pesticide may be depicted as follows along with some of the HFP used as fungicide.

(Dotted line indicates fragments of potential ligands)

Since pesticides are applied to the soil in amounts 0.1–0.5 kg per hectare; the actual concentration in plant can be much smaller. Given such low levels a xenobiotic will only have a pronounced biological effect if it attacks the plant's regulatory systems or interact with the substrates in plant-cell. Such substrates may consists of ions, or molecular com-

plexes of microelements. The role of microelements in biochemical processes is well documented^{7,8}. The metal ions which occur in cell perform various functions: polarize different part of enzyme molecule, alter their reactivity or serve as a matrix in which substrates and enzyme are oriented relative to one another. The functional property of some of the metalloenzymes is depicted⁹ in Table 1.

Table 1. Functional property of some of metalloenzymes

Enzyme	Catalyzed reaction	Metal
Carboxypeptidase	Hydrolysis of peptides	Zn
Alkaline phosphatase	Hydrolysis of phosphoric acid esters	Zn
Carbonic anhydrase	Hydration	Zn
Alcohol dehydrogenase	Dehydrogenation (NAD)	Zn
Aldonase	Attachment via carbonyl group	Zn
Glycoldehydrase	Rearrangement	Co
Carboxytrans-phosphorylase	Transfer of the phosphate group	Co
Phenoloxidase	Oxidation (multifunctional oxidase)	Cu (Fe)
Cytochromeoxidase	Oxidation (last link in electron transfer cytochrome chain)	Cu (Fe)
Pyruvic acid oxidase	Oxidation	Mn
Cytochrome C	Electron transfer	Fe
Ferridoxin	Electron transfer	Fe
Xanthine oxidase	Oxidation	Fe, Mo

The selective binding patterns for each of the elements by a particular ligand group follows the HSAB (hard-soft acid-base) principle. Some of the nucleophiles presents in the enzyme and their preference for particular metal ions are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Some of the nucleophilic atoms present in the enzymes

Electron donor atoms	Metal 'preferred' by proteins	Enzymes
-O ⁻	Ca, Mg, Mn	ATPase, enolase
-N, -O ⁻	Fe, Co, Ni	Carbonic anhydrase
-N, -S ⁻	Cu, Zn	Carboxy peptidase
RS ⁻	Zn, Mo	Alcohol dehydrogenase, xanthine oxidase

Many heterofunctional pesticides which contain one or many ligand groups have shown remarkable correspondence between their structure and activity with respect to metal ions. Thus, a classification has been developed in which the heterofunctional pesticide-structure is grouped by chemical

characteristics of heteroatoms in the ligand and also by the structural topological feature of ligands and their metal complexes^{10,11}.

The mechanisms by which ligands operate are not common to all fungicides. Fungicides are expected to possess a certain capability to form complexes with particular metals. The heterofunctional pesticides form complexes with the metal salts bringing considerable changes in the physico-chemical properties of the latter. It has been well studied that HFP are strong inhibitor of some metal-containing and metal-dependent enzymatic systems. These concept certainly offers strong possibilities for a directed synthesis of efficient and selective heterofunctional fungicides.

Furthermore, ligands containing sulphur and/or nitrogen donor atoms are likely to be most effective since they confer lipid solubility upon complexation and form stable complexes with class (b) and border-line metals. Of course the resultant activity takes into account the steric, electronic and pharmacokinetic factors but chelation² reduces the polarity of metal ion considerably because of the partial sharing of its positive charge with donor groups and delocalization of π -electrons over the whole chelate ring. This increases the lipid solubility of metal chelates, hence favours its permeation through lipid layer of the fungus membrane in case of antifungal studies.

Ligands bearing imidazole group or substituted by other heterocycles had been studied^{12,13} since very early time. Imidazole ring in a histidine moiety and the benzimidazole ring particularly and its dimethyl derivatives function as ligands towards transition metal ions in a variety of biologically important molecules including iron-heme systems, vitamin B-12 and its derivative as well as several metalloproteins^{14,15}. The strategy followed in the synthesis of various types of benzimidazole derivatives is also well documented¹⁶. Several benzimidazole derivatives used as chelating agents for transition metals have been prepared and well characterized¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

In addition to these heterocycles, the therapeutic importance of other five-membered heterocycles like 1,2,4-triazoles, 1,3,4-thiadiazoles and 1,3,4-oxadiazoles is also recognized^{20,21} owing to their great importance because of the availability of donor sites which have been complexed with the metal ions extensively²²⁻²⁵. A great deal of work on triazoles containing oxygen and sulphur donors at positions 3 and 5 of the triazole ring has also been reported in the literature²⁶⁻²⁸. Later on, earlier paper by Barlin²⁹ dealing with various condensed heterocycles has been found of great interest owing to the presence of potential donor sites for complexations with metal ions.

Thus the potential applications of azole complexes with the metals resulted in several publications³⁰⁻³². Furthermore, the capability of azomethine groups to act as a donor to metal ions had been of great interest since long time in which the metal ion catalysis in the hydrolysis of Schiff bases has been well studied by Eichhorn and Bailar³³.

Another interesting class of heterocycles bearing nitrogen and sulphur donors are thiazoles whose enzymatic activities depend upon their metallation^{34,35}.

In our study³⁶, we observed that 4-amino-5-carbethoxy-3-phenylthiazolin-2-thione (1) coordinates to the metal ions through both the nitrogen and sulphur atoms and the presence of phenyl group adjacent to nitrogen of the thiazole ring causes the lone-pair of nitrogen to lie in a plane different to that of the C=S plane preventing the coordination of the ring nitrogen to the same metal. Thus, these possible difference in the mode of coordination could be responsible for different properties of the complexes. Additionally, thiazoles have a strong aromatic character and in this respect it showed a strong relationship to pyridine³⁶.

The activity (% inhibition) observed for the Cr^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of the thiazoline ligand (1) against the fungi *Sclerotinia-Sclerotiorum*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Curvularia* was found to be significant³⁵, and chelation² theory does apply in this case; however, the potential role of anions and the type of fungi also played significant role. As compared to commercial fungicides like mancozeb, ziram, thiram and cuprorum, these metal complexes were rated to be a second generation fungicide. Thus, due to the importance of multifunctional heterocycles, we further concentrated

on the fungitoxicity of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes³⁷ with 5-hydroxy-3-methyl-4,5-methyldithiocarbonylate-1-phenylpyrazole (2).

The activity trend observed against *R. solani* and *H. oryzae* again emphasized the importance of chelation of the heterocycle with metal ions. However, beside this parameter, the physical properties like absorption of the complexes by microorganism was also noted to be very important factor in this system.

In continuation, we synthesized some N₂S₂-donors bearing hydrophobic group (alkyl chain) and after complexation with the metal ions³⁸ (Fig. 1) they were screened for their antifungal properties against similar fungi *H. oryzae* and *R. solani* and it was noted that the activity increases with increasing hydrophobicity, which is consistent with the chelation theory².

During the course of these study it was noticed that in a very early stage the fusion of thiazole ring with the benzimidazole resulting into thiabendazole show potential fungistatic and antimycotic properties, and its mode of coordination was studied by Vlandschoot *et al.*³⁹ who found

Fig. 1. N₂S₂ donor and its metal complexes.

that thiabendazole (L; III) is strongly coordinating ligand to the transition metal ions yielding the compounds of the formula $M(L)_3(\text{anion})_2$ and $M(L)_2(\text{anion})_2$.

Thus, enthused by the activity of thiabendazole, we designed and synthesised⁴⁰ a series of heterocycles by condensing benzimidazole ring with the potential heterocycles like 1,3,4-oxadiazoles, 1,2,4-triazoles and 1,3,4-thiadiazoles (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Bis-heterocycles.

The free ligands⁴⁰ (L) and their complexes⁴¹ $ML(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ ($M = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ and Zn^{II}) were screened against *H. oryzae* and *R. solani* for their fungitoxicity, and it was observed that the role of individual heterocycle though influences the activity yet the overall activity is again found to be correlated with the chelating ability of the heterocycles with metal ions. Furthermore, the encouraging results of

these bis-heterocycles prompted us to consider the importance of 2,4-pentanedione coupled with the diazonium salts of heterocycles (Fig. 3) used as a precursor of antimicrobial triazines⁴²⁻⁴⁴.

The fungitoxicity of these ligands (L_1 - L_6) and their dinuclear/polynuclear Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes in presence and in absence of 1,6-diaminohexane (Fig. 4) was determined against *Alternaria brassicae* and *Fusarium lycopersici* (crop damaging fungi) using spore germination method⁴⁵.

In general, about 40% inhibition showing Pd^{II} complexes even at 250 ppm solution in DMSO, was rated to be quite significant as compared to commercial fungicide dithane M-45, since metal complexes were found to be better fungitoxic than free ligands and chelation was found to be important factor for fungitoxicities. However, according to Kosower and Miyadera⁴⁶, the reactivity of azo compounds towards thiol groups of enzymes may also be important for better fungicidal properties of azo-systems.

During our studies as mentioned above, we came across recent finding by Mingos' group^{47,48} which opens a new way of metallo-drug design, where metal complexes are used to recognise the nucleoside bases. Mingos' group inspired from the mode of binding of square-planar Pt^{II} with DNA (in *cis*-platin) allowed to react another square-planar complex, bis(dithiobiureto)nickel(II) with uracil in DMSO and got $\{\text{Ni}(\text{dithiobiureto})_2(\text{uracil})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\}$. In this complex (Fig. 5) the basic uracil-Ni(btb)₂-uracil unit is further extended via additional NH-O hydrogen bonds and weaker NH...S interactions. Thus, the bifunctionality of a promising complex especially of Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} was utilised to

Fig. 3. Azolo-ligands.

For $L_3W = Cl; L_4, W=H, M = Pd(II)$ and $Pt(II)$

a

, $X = Y = OH_2, M = Ni(II); L = L_5, X = OH_2, Y = Nil, M = Cu(II)$
 , $X = Cl, Y = OH_2, M = Ni(II); L = L_6, X = Cl, Y = Nil, M = Cu(II)$

b

$L = L_5, X = OH_2; L = L_6, X = Cl$

c

Fig. 4. Proposed structures of the complexes with azolo-ligands (a, b, c).

bind nucleoside bases through weaker bonding and directed a new dimension for metallo-drug design.

Fig. 5. 'Base-pairing' of two uracil molecules to the square-planar nickel(II) complex, bis(dithiobiureto)nickel.

Thus keeping the above method of metallo-drug design in view and the bioactivity of thiouracils^{49,50} and their interaction with metal ions, we recently⁵¹ exploited 4-(*m*-chlorophenyl)-5-cyano-2-thiouracil for its complexation with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} acetate salts (Fig. 6).

Here, the multifunctionality of thiouracils is used instead of the metal complex in view of the fact that after complex-

$M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$ and Zn^{II}

Fig. 6. Metal acetate linked thiouracil derivative.

ation few groups like NH would be left for hydrogen bond formation with the nucleoside bases as described by Mingos *et al.* in addition to another donor like CN which is left for its further complexation with the essential elements like iron etc. necessary for the enzymatic activity of microorganism hence hampering the life-cycle of the microorganism. To our great surprise, the same was found true when the metal complexes of the thiouracil (L) (Fig. 6) were allowed to interact with the fungi *H. oryzae* and *R. solani*. The complexes $\{\text{CuL}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\}$ and $\{\text{ZnL}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\}$ showed very significant activity (80–100% inhibition) without any phytotoxicity.

Further, to check the above surmise, we reacted the stoichiometric amount of the complexes with FeCl_3 in DMSO and the resulting reddish brown compounds showed the participation of its C=N group with the Fe^{III} as in its ir ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ of the free thiouracil (L) shifted from ~ 2220 to $\sim 2180 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes). Our attempt of exploiting the hydrogen bond formation by NH groups of thiouracil (L) with other nucleoside bases is still in way.

This brief review thus conveys that (i) the heterocycles have potential chance to be bioactive upon their chelation with the metal ions, (ii) the heterocycles with multifunctionality have always greater chance of their interaction either with the nucleoside bases (even after complexation with the metal ions) or with the biologically essential metal ions present in the biosystem and (iii) coordinatively unsaturated metal present in metal complexes could be a promising candidate as a fungicide since they would always attempt to interact especially with some of the enzymatic functional groups in order to achieve higher coordination number.

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Mishra : Chelation and fungitoxicity

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